

ANALYZING THE MARKET OF COUGH SYRUPS REGISTERED IN THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract: This paper presents the results of marketing research on the market of cough syrups. The necessity of developing new original syrups based on phytosubstances is shown, as well as the need to expand the range of medicinal cough syrups produced in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The pharmaceutical market is an important sector of the economy of any country and is a criterion of its economic and social development, the level of well-being of the population. In connection with the above, the analysis of the assortment of cough syrups of the market of the Republic of Kazakhstan was carried out.

Keywords: Cough syrup, pharmaceutical market, state register, market analysis

Introduction

1.1 Relevance of respiratory diseases in Republic of Kazakhstan

According to new estimates from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) of the United States, the World Health Organization (WHO), and global health partners, up to 650,000 people die each year from respiratory diseases caused by seasonal influenza. This is higher than the previous global estimate of 250,000–500,000 deaths, calculated over a decade ago, which covered all influenza-related death cases, including those from cardiovascular diseases and diabetes. The new figures, ranging from 290,000 to 650,000 deaths, are based on more recent data from a broader and more diverse range of countries, including those with lower-than-average income levels, and do not include deaths from non-respiratory diseases. The prevalence of chronic cough has been estimated at between 3% and 40% of the population. A survey by the European Respiratory Society of 18 277 subjects aged 20–48 years from 16 countries worldwide reported nocturnal cough in 30%, productive cough in 10%, and non-productive cough in 10%.

Following database World Health Organization in 2021 the number of deaths is reached to 14487 people in Kazakstan. Including 8258 male and 6229 female.[Table 1]

1.2.The main direction of marketing research is the development of the choice of medicines. Its completeness, the degree of renewal play an important role and are taken into account both when prescribing and when choosing medicines . The main approach to understanding the pharmaceutical market is content analysis, i.e. a method of quantitative analysis of documents that allows you to get a detailed idea of the selected group of products or therapeutic group of medicines.[1]

To present, cough is one of the most common symptoms of acute respiratory viral diseases. Cough is one of the mechanisms of cleansing the respiratory tract. It is not a specific sign of any disease and can be triggered by the following factors:

- inflammatory reactions from the upper and lower respiratory tract (with laryngitis, bronchitis, bronchiolitis, pneumonia or lung abscess) [2];
- mechanical irritation – inhalation of dust, violation of the patency of the bronchi due to an increase in their tone or compression (tumors of the lungs or mediastinum, aortic aneurysm, foreign bodies, contraction of smooth muscles of the respiratory tract in bronchial asthma)
- chemical irritation – inhalation of gases with a strong odor(for example, tobacco smoke) [3];
- thermal irritation – inhalation of very hot or very cold air.

The purpose of the study

Analysing the market of cough syrups registered in the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Methods and materials

Official publication State Register of Medicines of the Republic of Kazakhstan and static methods.

Results:

As a result of the study of cough syrups included in the State Register of Medicines of the Republic of Kazakhstan for March 2023, it was found that the total number of medicines is 7379, of which there are 81 cough syrups, which is 1% (Fig. 1).

Figure-1

Further analysis showed that the ratio of syrups based on phytosubstantial and synthetic, included in the State Register for 2023, is 79.5% to 20.5% (Table 1).

Table 1- Classification of syrup according to the State Register of Medicinal Products of the Republic of Kazakhstan After that was carried out analysis of the ratio of syrups of domestic and foreign (Table 2, Figure 3).

Syrup bases	Total number	Specific gravity, %
synthetic	38	50%
phytosubstantial	38	50%

From Table 2 and Figure 3 it follows that the State Register of Medicines of the Republic of Kazakhstan is dominated by syrups of foreign production, their share is 78%, and domestic – 22%.

Table 2- Syrups of domestic and foreign manufacturers in the State Register of Medicines of the Republic of Kazakhstan (absolute and relative indicators)

Countries	Quantity of syrups	Specific gravity,%
Kazakhstan	17	22%
Foreign countries	59	78%

Figure 3 - Syrups of domestic and foreign manufacturers

The analysis of syrups from foreign manufacturers is given in Table 3. Table 3 shows that 10 countries supply syrups to Kazakhstan. The largest number of syrups registered in Kazakhstan comes from Germany (14%), India (13%), Pakistan (10%) Ukraine (7%), Turkey(7%).

Table 3- Foreign manufactures of syrups

№	Producing country	Amount of syrups	Specific gravity,%
1	Germany	11	14%
2	India	9	13%
3	Pakistan	7	10%
4	Ukraine	5	7%
5	Turkey	5	7%
6	Slovenia	4	5%
7	Bulgaria	4	5%
8	Italy	3	4%
9	Austria	2	3%
10	Egypt	2	3%
11	France	1	1%
12	Czech republic	1	1%
13	Hungary	1	1%
14	Poland	1	1%
15	Belorussia	1	1%
16	Russia	1	1%
17	Latvia	1	1%

Conclusion

During the segmentation analysis, it was found that for the production of expectorant syrups that are on the market of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the share of foreign-made medicines is 78% and only 22% domestic. The leaders among foreign manufacturers are Germany and India. The analysis showed the advantage of imported medicines, which dictates the need to create new domestic medicines, in this case, cough syrups based on phytosubstances.

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